

Glossary

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Preamble

We selected the following terms and concepts either because we used them in our manuscript or because they are crucial to understanding the references we cited. The material in here was largely taken from [YBYRÁ's glossary](#). For manuscript's details and contact information, see Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3740770](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3740770)).

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Phylogenetic terms and concepts

Ambiguous optimization

Characters that are ambiguously **optimized** have more than one possible **optimization** on a tree.

Ancestors

See **nodes**.

Apomorphy

A **character-state** that is derived from an ancestral (**plesiomorphic**) **character-state** in a transformation event.

Autapomorphy

An autapomorphy is an **apomorphy** that is unique to a **terminal** or **taxon**.

See the illustration in “**synapomorphy**” with different types of transformations.

Branch

The branch is an edge connecting two **nodes**.

Character

Characters are features that can be compared among taxa.

Characters are conceptualized as “transformation series”. As such, characters are historical individuals akin to species and clades.

Different characters that are to be regarded as transformation stages of the same original character are generally called **homologous**.

In the context of **tree** search in phylogenetic analysis, a character is a fixed column in a data matrix.

Character-state

One of the various conditions of a **character**. Characters states can be regarded as **transformation** stages of the same original **character**.

In the context of **tree** search in phylogenetic analysis, the character-states are the variation on a fixed column in a data matrix (i.e., variation of a **character**).

Character optimization

In YBYRÁ, **character** optimization refers to the optimal distribution of **transformations** on a **tree** under the **parsimony** criterion.

Clade

- All the descendants from a single common and unique **ancestor**.
- All the **terminals** derived from the same **node** in a **tree**

See the illustration in “**monophyletic group**.”

Cladograms

See **trees**.

Cost

Under the parsimony criterion, costs refers to the number of **transformations events** on a **tree**.

Homology

Attributes that are shared due to common ancestry are homologous (e.g., see Wheeler 2006 and Nixon & Carpenter 2012).

Homologous attributes can be traced back to a single **transformation event** on a **branch** of a **cladogram**.

Homoplasy

Homoplasy is error or incongruence in the codification of characters (see Nixon & Carpenter 2012).

Homoplasious **character-states** do not, by definition, identify the same historical entity. These characters have a non-minimal number of **transformations** on a **tree**.

See the illustration in “**monophyletic group**.”

HTUs

Hypothetical taxonomic units.

Each internal **node** is an HTU.

Ingroup

The ingroup is a putative clade composed of the terminals whose relationships are the primary focus of study (Grant 2019). The ingroup is often referred to as the study group (Janies 2019).

Leaf

See [terminals](#).

Match split distance

The match split (MS) distance for unrooted binary phylogenetic trees is defined by Bogdanowicz & Giaro (2012) as the cost of the best global assignment between the internal edges of the two trees being compared.

According to Bogdanowicz & Giaro (2012: 159), “the MS distance is more sensitive than RF and is resistant to displacement of a small number of leaves”.

Match split distance

- The best match between 2 splits is chosen by counting the number of terminals that are different between each subtree and scaling by 0.5
- In this example, the best match is between **ac|bde** and **de|abc** and the MS distance between these 2 unrooted trees is **1**.

Monophyletic group

A natural group composed of a unique common ancestor and all its descendants. See [clade](#).

Monophyletic

Examples of other paraphyletic groups on this image: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 1+2+3, 1+2+3+4, 1+2+3+4+5. Note that the monophyly of 1+2+3+4+5 cannot be tested because the complete set of terminals will always be monophyletic.

Mutation

When understood in the context of a **rooted tree**, the **SNPs** or **AA variants** become mutations. Mutations are polarized variations (**transformations**) in nucleotide (**DNA** or **RNA**) and **AA** sequences.

Newick

Newick format is the tree file format used by GARLI, MrBayes, PAUP*, **PHYLIP**, PROTML, TREE-PUZZLE, and several other programs. Very few programs cannot read or import this tree file format. However, Newick is the only tree file format readable by the **PHYLIP** programs *drawgram*, *drawtree*, and *retree*.

In the Newick format, **terminals** are separated by commas and the **sister-group** relationships are represented by nested parenthesis. Here are a few examples of **trees** in the Newick format:

- **Example 1:** minimal representation

```
((A,B),C);
```

- **Example 2:** a tree with branch lengths

```
((A:5,B:7):10,C:3);
```

- **Example 3:** a tree with node labels and branch lengths

```
((A:5,B:7)Ancestor:10,C:3);
```

NNI

Nearest-neighbor interchange (NNI) is the least rigorous swapping approach (in comparison to [SPR](#) and [TBR](#)). There are two possible NNI rearrangements per internal [branch](#). For a tree with n taxa, there are $n-3$ internal branches. Thus, there are $2(n-3)$ NNI rearrangements for any [tree](#).

Nodes

That point of intersection in a [tree](#) that identifies a component. Internal nodes can be called hypothetical taxonomic units ([HTUs](#)). Leaf nodes can be called operational taxonomic unities ([OTUs](#)).

Optimality criterion

The optimality criterion is the scoring criterion used for selecting the most optimal hypotheses among all others. Same as optimality score. In the context of multiple sequence alignment, the optimality criterion, or score, is the objective function used to measure [MSA](#) quality (e.g., sum-of-pairs, Shannon entropy, and phylogenetic tree cost). In the context of cladistic search, the optimality criterion refers to the different scoring systems used to select [trees](#) (e.g., tree length in parsimony, likelihood score in maximum likelihood, and posterior probability in Bayesian inference).

Optimality score

See [optimality criterion](#).

OTUs

Operational taxonomic units. See [terminals](#).

Outgroup

The outgroup may refer to a taxon and its data, chosen by the user, to [root](#) the tree (Janies 2019). Often a user will choose an outgroup that is a closely related lineage to the study group (i.e., the [ingroup](#)). Alternatively, a virologist interested in the phylogenetics of different strain of viruses might use an isolate of the same strain collected earlier than the study group as an outgroup (Janies 2019). Also, see "[outgroup comparison](#)."

Outgroup comparison

[Outgroup](#) comparison is usually conceptualized operationally as a method for [rooting](#) the [topology](#) and directing or polarizing character transformations (Farris, 1972, 1982), thereby converting a net- work of abstract connections into a theory of concrete evolutionary events (Lundberg, 1972). See discussion in Grant (2019).

PHYLIP

PHYLIP is a phylogeny inference package of computer programs for inferring phylogenies. The package is available at <http://evolution.genetics.washington.edu/phylip.html>.

PHYLIP can only read trees in Newick format.

Paraphyletic

An unnatural group of taxa or OTUs that lacks exactly one monophyletic group to become monophyletic.

Paraphyletic

Examples of other paraphyletic groups on this image: 1+3+4, 2+3+4, 3+4.

Parsimony

Parsimony is an optimality criterion used to discriminate concurrent hypothesis based on the principle of cost minimization.

In phylogenetic systematics, the parsimony criterion is applied to select cladograms with minimal length.

Plesiomorphy

An ancestral character-state in a transformation event from which an apomorphic character-state is derived.

See the illustration in “synapomorphy.”

Polyphyletic

An unnatural group of Taxa or OTUs that lacks two or more monophyletic groups to become monophyletic.

Polyphyletic

Examples of other polyphyletic on this image: 1+3, 2+4, 1+2+3+5.

REP

The ratio of explanatory power (REP), as defined in Grant & Kluge (2007).

Robinson-Foulds distance

Originally proposed by Robinson & Foulds (1981).

The Robinson-Foulds distance (RF) is a metric for comparing two binary or nonbinary phylogenetic trees, by means of elementary operations (i.e. Bourque's "contraction" and "decontraction"; see Robinson & Foulds 1981: Fig. 2) which transform one tree into another.

The function of Bourque's contraction removes all edges from the first and second trees being compared. The function of Bourque's decontraction is then used to reconstruct the second tree. The number of operations in each of these procedures is equivalent to the number of edges in the first tree that are not in the second tree plus the number of edges in the second tree that are not in the first tree. The sum of the operations is equivalent to a transformation from one tree to another.

The displacement of a single OTU can change several nodes on the tree causing RF to overestimate the difference between two topologies in some cases.

Robinson-Foulds distance

- Using the “compression” of Boulger (α), we create $T_1 \wedge T_2$ (in blue)
- Using the “decompression” of Boulger (α^{-1}) we reconstruct T_2 (in red)
- The sum of the number of α and α^{-1} operations is the distance between T_1 and T_2

Figures above were taken from from Robinsol & Foulds (1981)

Root

The root determines the polarity of **character transformation** in a **cladogram**.

The root **node** is the only **node** in a rooted **tree** with degree 2 (i.e., it is connected to two other **nodes**).

YBYRÁ defines the root using a single root **terminal** (a degree 1 node).

Rooted tree

A **rooted tree** is a **cladogram** in which the polarity of **character transformation** is determined by the **root**.

NOTE: Trees in parenthetical notation (such as trees in **Newick** format) are polarized by the hierarchy of the nested parenthesis. However, some programs will treat those trees as unrooted unless the user specifies otherwise.

Sensitivity analysis

“In phylogenetic systematics, authors make use sensitivity analysis to address how much hypothesis choice may be affected by variables such as different tree search strategies, optimality criteria, alignment methods, and trans- formation cost schemes [Higdon et al. 2007, Miller et al. 2010]. There is some debate in the literature regarding the scientific and heuristic value of sensitivity analysis [Grant & Kluge 2005, Payne 2014]. However, the instrumental value of sensitivity analysis as means to describe and compare different methodological approaches in systematics is indisputable” (from Machado 2015).

Simultaneous analysis

Refers to the simultaneous analysis of multiple data sets in opposition to separate analysis of partitioned data followed by consensus of results. See “total evidence”.

Sister-group

In a binary **tree**, sister-groups are two groups that share a unique common-**ancestor** (**node**). Sister-groups are considered coeval and comparable.

Split

A split is the division of a **tree** into two **trees** by the removal of an edge.

For example, the **tree** (A,(C(D,(E,F)))) can be divided in two subtrees (E,F) and (A,(C,D)).

SPR

The subtree Pruning-Re-grafting (SPR) is a more rigorous swapping scheme than **NNI** but it is less rigorous than **TBR**. SPR operates by breaking all **branches** to make subtrees and grafting the subtrees onto each branch of the remaining **trees**. The idea is to generate subtrees by breaking each branch, and then re-grafting the subtrees in all possible ways. For a tree with n taxa, there will be $4(n-3)(n-2)$ SPR rearrangements.

Strict consensus

A strict consensus tree contains only the nodes that are present in all the **trees**.

In the manuscript, every consensus tree is a strict consensus tree except for the trees resulting from Bayesian inference, which are based on a majority rule.

Substitution

A mode of nucleotide (**DNA** or **RNA**) or **AA transformation**.

Symplesiomorphy

Symplesiomorphy is ancestral **character-state** that is shared by a non-**monophyletic** group of terminals.

See the illustration in “**synapomorphy**” with different types of transformations.

Synapomorphy

Synapomorphy refers to the shared occurrence of a derived (**apomorphic**) **character-state** in a monophyletic group, no matter whether or not the **character-state** is **homoplastic** (see Grant & Kluge 2004).

There is great debate over the equality of **homology** and **synapomorphy** (see Nixon & Carpenter 2012).

Synapomorphy, symplesiomorphy and autopomorphy

A single character with 2 character states, "0" and "1". At the level of the transformation in blue, "1" is a **synapomorphy** and "0" is a **symplesiomorphy**. At the level of the transformation in white, "0" is an **autopomorphy** and "1" is a **plesiomorphy**. Since this character cannot be optimized with minimal change, it is considered **homoplastic**.

Taxon (taxa)

A taxa is a group of organisms at any level of the systematic hierarchy.

Taxa are often represented as **terminals** and/or **clades** in a **cladogram**.

Terminals

A terminal is any object that occurs at the tips of a **tree** (also called **OTU** or leaf).

Terminals often represent **taxa**.

TBR

The **tree** bisection-reconnection (TBR) algorithm is the most rigorous strategy for **branch** swapping (in comparison to **NNI** and **SPR**). All branches are bisected, and reconnected in all possible ways. It's not possible to generalize how many TBR rearrangements could be made for a tree of a given size (as we could with **NNI** and **SPR**), but TBR swapping searches tree space more thoroughly than **NNI** and **SPR**.

Topology

See **trees**.

Total evidence

Often used as a synonymous of "**simultaneous analysis**". Also used in opposition to partitioned analysis. Some authors argue that the term "total evidence" should be restricted

to analysis which use all data, while “[simultaneous-analysis](#)” should refer to the analysis of multiple data sets with as much data included as is appropriate and tractable. See Kluge (1989) and Nixon & Carpenter (1996).

Transformations

According to Wheeler (2012), sequences of elements can undergo several modes of transformation (e.g., [substitution](#), insertion–deletion, inversion, and move). Also, transformations can occur in complex combinations (e.g., inversion + move) making their reconstruction in systematic analysis complex. For example, see the sequences of transformations below:

x₀, x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅ → x₀, x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅
x₀, x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅ → x₀, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₆, x₅
x₀, x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅ → x₀, x₁, x₄, x₃, x₂, x₅
x₀, x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅ → x₀, x₃, x₄, x₅, x₁, x₂

In the four different sequence of transformations above, line no. 1 shows a substitution, line no. 2 shows a insertion–deletion, line no. 3 shows an inversion, and line no. 4 shows a move.

Transformations are an important concept in phylogenetics. Hennig (1966) established the important distinction between features that are [homologous](#) and shared by ancestors and descendants ([symplesiomorphy](#)) and features that have changed in a group of descendants ([synapomorphy](#)). This later would allow Farris (1970) and Fitch (1971) to create algorithms that connected this character-based approach to inferring phylogenies with [optimality criteria](#) applied to assess trees based on the amount of transformations the trees implied.

Transformations are connected to the concepts of polarity (in the sense of order or direction) and [outgroup comparison](#). For example, Watrous and Wheeler (1981) established the importance of using an outgroup to [root](#) the [trees](#) and infer the polarity of the [transformation events](#).

Transformations in nucleotide ([DNA](#) or [RNA](#)) and [AA](#) sequences are called [mutations](#).

Transformation events

Transformation events are real historical processes of evolution (see Grant & Kluge 2004).

Transformation series

See [character](#).

TREAD

The program Hennig86 produces output trees that has a “tread” and the [trees](#) in parenthetical notation. This is called the TREAD or Hennig86 [tree](#) format.

Multiples trees are separated by “*”. The last tree ends in a semicolon. Comments can be made after “tread” using single quote marks. For use in the program [TNT](#) it is common to include “proc-;” at the end of the file.

Example: several [trees](#) in TREAD format

```
tread 'this is a comment'  
(T1 (((T4 T2) T3 )((T5 T6) T7 )))*  
(T1 ((T4 (T2 T3 ))(T5 (T6 T7 ))))*  
(T1 ((T2 (T4 T3 ))(T5 (T6 T7 ))));  
proc-;
```

Trees

In here we are using trees, cladograms, and topology as interchangeable concepts (see discussion of the differences between these concepts in Wheeler 2012: p. 28).

The phylogenetic tree is a primary tool for describing evolutionary relationships. Trees are connected, acyclic graphs representing nested [sister-group](#) relationships. Trees in YBYRÁ are in parenthetical notation following the [Newick \(PHYLIP\)](#) or [Hennig86 \(TREAD\)](#) format.

Unrooted tree

An [unrooted tree](#) is a [cladogram](#) in which the polarity of [character transformation](#) is not determined.

Variant

Variants refer to nucleotide ([DNA](#) or [RNA](#)) or [AA](#) sequence variants or phenotypic character variants. These are non-polarized changes that therefore differ from [transformations](#) (such as [mutations](#)).

Other terms and concepts

AA

Amino acids (AAs) are a set of 20 different molecules used to build proteins. Proteins consist of one or more chains of amino acids called polypeptides. The sequence of the amino acid chain causes the polypeptide to fold into a shape that is biologically active. The amino acid sequences of proteins are encoded in the genes. See illustration below, taken from NIH's National Human Genome Research Institute (<https://www.genome.gov/genetics-glossary/Amino-Acids>).

Amino Acids

Ala: Alanine	Gln: Glutamine	Leu: Leucine	Ser: Serine
Arg: Arginine	Glu: Glutamic acid	Lys: Lysine	Thr: Threonine
Asn: Asparagine	Gly: Glycine	Met: Methionine	Trp: Tryptophane
Asp: Aspartic acid	His: Histidine	Phe: Phenylalanine	Tyr: Tyrosine
Cys: Cysteine	Ile: Isoleucine	Pro: Proline	Val: Valine

ACE2

Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2).

AlphaCoV

Members of the genus *Alphacoronavirus*, a group of CoVs.

BetaCoV

Members of the genus *Betacoronavirus*, a group of CoVs.

CoV

A coronavirus (CoV) is a virus that belongs to the subfamily *Orthocoronavirinae* (formally known as *Coronavirinae*) in the family *Coronaviridae*, order *Nidovirales*). There are four genera of coronaviruses: *Alphacoronavirus* ([AlphaCoV](#)), *Betacoronavirus* ([BetaCoV](#)), *Gammacoronavirus* ([GammaCoV](#)), and *Deltacoronavirus* ([DeltaCoV](#)).

COVID-19

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by [SARS-CoV-2](#). Read the [WHO's](#) internet page on COVID-19 at <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>.

DeltaCoV

Members of the genus *Deltacoronavirus*, a group of [CoVs](#).

DNA

The deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), is the hereditary material in humans and almost all other organisms. See <http://www.informatics.jax.org/glossary/dna>.

DPP4

The dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP4) receptor.

GammaCoV

Members of the genus *Gammacoronavirus*, a group of [CoVs](#).

GISAID

The Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID). The origins of GISAID are described in Shu & McCauley (2017). The GISAID's homepage is available at <https://www.gisaid.org/>.

HCoV

A human coronavirus (HCoV) is a [CoV](#) that is known to infect humans.

ICTV

International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV). See the ICTV's homepage at <https://talk.ictvonline.org/>.

kb

Kilobase (kb): 1,000 bases of DNA or RNA.

MERS

The Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) is an illness caused by a **CoV** called Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (**MERS-CoV**).

MERS-CoV

The Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), which causes **MERS**.

MSA

Multiple sequence alignment (MSA).

NCBI

The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) advances science and health by providing access to biomedical and genomic information. Visit the NCBI's homepage is available at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.

nm

Nanometer (nm): one billionth of a meter.

RBM

Receptor binding motif (RBM).

RNA

The ribonucleic acid (RNA) is the primary product of gene expression. Chemically, it differs from **DNA** by the substitution of ribose for deoxyribose in the sugar-phosphate backbone and by the substitution of the base uracil for thymine. See <http://www.informatics.jax.org/glossary/rna>.

SARS

The severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) is an illness caused by a **CoV** called severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (**SARS-CoV-1**).

SARS-CoV

Same as **SARS-CoV-1**.

SARS-CoV-1

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (**SARS-CoV-1**; also referred to as SARS-CoV), which causes **SARS**.

SARS-CoV-2

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (**SARS-CoV-2**; not the same as **SARS-CoV**), which causes **COVID-19**.

SNP

Single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP).

ssRNA (+)

A positive-sense, single-stranded RNA (+ ssRNA).

WHO

The World Health Organization (WHO). See the WHO's homepage at <https://www.who.int/>.

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